

Fibre / matrix compatibility
in new cold-cure phenolic resin-based composites.

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INTRODUCTION

Phenolic resins have been known for a long time, in fact the reaction between phenols and aldehydes was first described by Baeyer in 1872 (1). After the findings of Baekeland (2) in the early years of the twentieth century, phenolic resins were one of the most important and widely-used polymers to be produced.

More recently, with the appearance of other thermosetting resins like polyesters and epoxies, interest in phenolic resins waned, but today their excellent properties of fire-resistance and low smoke emission give them widespread application in uses where high temperatures are encountered (3).

Traditional phenolics have several disadvantages for large composite structures: poor fibre / matrix compatibility, ineffectiveness of fibre finishes and sizing treatments, and the high curing temperatures required; and their use has been restricted despite the fact that their high-temperature properties are superior to those of other thermosetting matrix resins.

The new acid-catalysed cold-cure phenolics overcome many of the above disadvantages. They offer low viscosity, low contents of free phenol and formaldehyde, and are suitable for processing by hand layup and RIM or RTM (4). With the modern emphasis on fire safety in public transport, very large potential markets exist for these resins as matrices for GRP.

In this work, we have used differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) to study the curing process of a cold-cure phenolic resin, and the effect of the presence of fibres on the whole curing cycle. We used as reinforcements plain glass fibres, and glass fibres previously sized with appropriate silane coupling agents.

Using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), we have sought an understanding of the chemical processes in the formation of a cold-cure phenolic resin from a liquid resin during the curing reaction at different temperatures, with and without the presence of reinforcement.

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EXPERIMENTAL

The resin used was "Cellobond J2027L", a second-generation cold-cure phenolic resol for the manufacture of fibre-reinforced composites, supplied, with its proprietary catalyst "Phencat 10", by BP Chemicals Ltd. This resin can be cured at temperatures from ambient to 70C. In all tests the catalyst concentration used was 7% by weight. The reinforcement was E-glass fibre, supplied by Owens Corning UK Ltd. The following coupling agents, supplied by Union Carbide Corporation, were used as received:

gamma-aminopropyltriethoxysilane	(code: A1100).
n-beta-aminoethyl-gamma-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane	(code: A1120).
gamma-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane	(code: A187).

Temperatures and enthalpies relating to the curing of the resin were determined using a DuPont 910 DSC, equipped with a calorimetric cell that allows temperature scanning from -170 to 600C.

For FTIR work a Model 1720X spectrometer by Perkin Elmer was used. Samples were mixed with KBr powder, mounted in a Specac diffuse reflectance accessory, and scanned at a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹, twenty to thirty scans of each sample being collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The DSC thermograms obtained from plain liquid phenolic resin heated from -30 to 300C are characterised by three different peaks. A small endotherm occurs at 30C, perhaps due to the melting of free phenol, or alternatively to reorganisations in hydrogen bonding, which are characteristic of hydroxyl groups, particularly in the presence of water. Secondly, a strong exotherm at 74C is ascribed to the curing reaction. Thirdly, at 100C there is a very strong endotherm, attributed to evaporation of water condensed by the crosslinking reaction.

By contrast, samples containing glass fibres present an endothermic peak for water evaporation having the same enthalpic value, but spread over a wide temperature range, and centring on a higher temperature. This suggests a delayed release of condensed water, indicating that the curing reaction in the presence of glass fibres is incomplete, leaving water imprisoned in the imperfectly-crosslinked network.

An exception to this behaviour was observed in samples containing one of the three coupling agents listed above: A1100 (gamma-aminopropyltriethoxysilane). These showed much more rapid evaporation of the condensed water.

In further experiments, after isothermal curing of phenolic / glass samples incorporating the different coupling agents, DSC was used to determine the residual curing heat. This indicates the degree of cure achieved in the first treatment. Here the samples incorporating A1100 showed the lowest residual curing heat, giving promise of improved stability of resin properties over time.

Studies using FTIR have yielded information concerning:

- (a) Species present in uncured resin, such as the methylol content.
- (b) The competing cure reactions. For example, ether-linkage formation has been found to predominate at low curing temperatures (20C), whereas methylene-linkage formation predominates at higher temperatures (60C).

Additionally, we are attempting to follow the reactions at the interface between phenolic resin and sized glass fibres, using attenuated total reflectance (ATR) spectroscopy. Preliminary results suggest that the presence of treated glass does not inhibit the curing reaction, but this contradiction of the DSC results cannot be resolved until quantitative analysis has been performed on the reactive groups participating in the cure. FTIR work is continuing to this end.

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